

Original Research Paper

INCIDENCE AND PROGNOSTIC INDEX OF SECONDARY BACTERIAL INFECTION IN COVID 19 PNEUMONIA.

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ABSTRACT:

Aim & Objectives: 1.To study incidence of secondary bacterial infection in covid 19 pneumonia, 2.To find the outcome of covid 19 patient with concomitant infection. **Material and Methods:** This is a Single Centre, Retrospective medical record based cohort study done in inpatients of COVID -19 RTPCR positive with clinically and Radiological findings suggestive of COVID -19 at Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. **Results:** Based on culture findings, about 15% of the COVID19 patients had secondary bacterial infection. The commonest bacteria were Pseudomonas followed by E. coli, Klebsiella and Enterococci. Diabetes is a major risk factor for the secondary bacterial infection among COVID 19 patients.

Keywords: Secondary Bacterial Infection, Pseudomonas, E. Coli., Diabetes Pateint, Covid-19

INTRODUCTION:

Coronavirus disease is the greatest ongoing global pandemic of our generation. The novel virus was first identified in the Chinese city of Wuhan in December 2019. COVID 19 symptoms range from none to life threatening . Most people infected with the virus shows symptoms of mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without any medical management ; while few progress to severe illness leading to death. COVID 19 patients with diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), Cardiovascular disease (CVD), Hypertension , Malignancies ,HIV and other comorbidities could develop a life threatening situation. People with chronic respiratory illness such as bronchiectasis, TB, diabetics are generally more prone for secondary bacterial infection. In the recent studies done on covid 19 patients, it was found that secondary infections were significantly associated with worse outcomes and death despite antimicrobial therapies. The concomitant infections described included other respiratory viruses, bacteria, including mycobacteria, fungi. Co infections can modify the virulence of the virus and cell death, therefore altering disease severity. They lead COVID 19 patient into a vicious infectious circle of life and are substantially associated with significant mortality and morbidity. In order to understand the possible organisms and the pattern of occurrence of the secondary bacterial infections, detailed investigations need to be done on the characteristics of patients and their bacteriological

findings. Diagnosing secondary infection in COVID 19 patients will help to improve the clinical outcome and mortality and to warrant extra caution to prevent the occurrence of secondary bacterial infection and to practice appropriate antimicrobial stewardship. In this context a retrospective study will be helpful to understand the incidence, pattern and the prognosis of patients with secondary bacterial infection and steps required to prevent its occurrence in COVID 19 patients.

METHODOLOGY:

This is a retrospective medical record based cohort analysis of COVID 19 infected patients for secondary bacterial infection; admitted at Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital between March 2021 to June 2021. Prior approval from the Scientific Research Committee and Institutional Ethics Committee will be sought. Information such as Age, gender, clinical presentation, co-morbidities, length of stay, disease severity, laboratory measurements, in-hospital mortality; were collected from medical records using a Pre specified Case Proforma. Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and statistical analysis were done.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data was entered in Microsoft Excel and analysis will be done using SPSS version 23.0 software. Categorical variable was expressed as percentages whereas continuous variables will be expressed as mean and

standard deviations. Comparisons was determined by Student's t test for continuous variables and by Chi-square test for categorical variables. Univariate and multivariate analysis was be performed to analyze the

association of clinical characteristics and laboratory parameters and mortality risk. A two-tailed p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

		Number	Percentage
Age category	≤40 years	9	12.5%
	41-50 years	16	22.2%
	51-60 years	23	31.9%
	61-70 years	10	13.9%
	>70 years	14	19.4%
Gender	Female	34	47.2%
	Male	38	52.8%

		Number	Percentage
Diabetes Mellitus	Present	33	45.8%
	Absent	39	54.2%
Systemic Hypertension	Present	32	44.4%
	Absent	40	55.6%
Coronary Artery Disease	Present	2	2.8%
	Absent	70	97.2%
Hypothyroidism	Present	7	9.7%
	Absent	65	90.3%

		Number	Percentage
Duration of Hospital stay	≤5 days	6	8.3%
	6-10 days	29	40.3%
	>10 days	37	51.4%
Severity of COVID19	Mild	16	22.2%
	Moderate	26	36.1%
	Severe	30	41.7%

		Duration of Hospital stay, n(%)			p value*
		≤5 days	6-10 days	>10 days	
Severity of COVID19	Mild	0	12 (41.4%)	4 (10.8%)	0.004[^]
	Moderate	1 (16.7%)	11 (37.9%)	14 (37.8%)	
	Severe	5 (83.3%)	6 (20.7%)	19 (51.4%)	

*p value by chi-square test(p<0.05)

		Number	Percentage
Culture findings	Bacterial Growth	11	15.3%
	Fungal growth	3	4.2%
	No growth/ Normal Flora	27	37.5%
	Not done	31	43%

		Culture findings, n(%)			p value*
		Bacterial Growth	Fungal Growth	Normal Growth/ Normal Flora	
Age category	≤40 years	1 (9.1%)	1 (33.3%)	3 (11.1%)	0.241
	41-50 years	6 (54.5%)	0	6 (22.2%)	
	51-60 years	2 (18.2%)	1 (33.3%)	8 (29.6%)	
	61-70 years	0	1 (33.3%)	6 (22.2%)	
	>70 years	2 (18.2%)	0	4 (14.8%)	

Gender	Female	5 (45.5%)	1 (33.3%)	11 (40.7%)	0.700
	Male	6 (54.5%)	2 (66.7%)	16 (59.3%)	
Duration of Hospital stay	≤5 days	1 (9.1%)	0	3 (11.1%)	0.714
	6-10 days	2 (18.2%)	1 (33.3%)	12 (44.4%)	
	>10 days	8 (72.7%)	2 (66.7%)	12 (44.4%)	
Diabetes Mellitus	Present	4 (36.4%)	2 (66.7%)	18 (66.7%)	0.027[^]
	Absent	7 (63.6%)	1 (33.3%)	9 (33.3%)	
Systemic Hypertension	Present	4 (36.4%)	2 (66.7%)	10 (37.0%)	0.545
	Absent	7 (63.6%)	1 (33.3%)	17 (63.0%)	
Coronary Artery Disease	Present	1 (9.1%)	0	0	0.475
	Absent	10 (90.9%)	3 (100.0%)	27 (100.0%)	
Hypothyroidism	Present	0	0 (0.0%)	2 (7.4%)	0.373
	Absent	11 (100.0%)	3 (100.0%)	25 (92.6%)	

**p value by chi-square test*

		Number	Percentage
Outcome	Death	13	18.1%
	Recovered	59	81.9%

Death occurred in 18% of the patients

		Outcome		p value*
		Death	Recovered	
Age category	≤40 years	0	9 (15.3%)	0.032[^]
	41-50 years	2 (15.4%)	14 (23.7%)	
	51-60 years	5 (38.5%)	18 (30.5%)	
	61-70 years	5 (38.5%)	5 (8.5%)	
	>70 years	1 (7.7%)	13 (22.0%)	
Gender	Female	5 (38.5%)	29 (49.2%)	0.485
	Male	8 (61.5%)	30 (50.8%)	

Duration of Hospital stay	≤5 days	6 (46.2%)	0	<0.001[^]
	6-10 days	3 (23.1%)	26 (44.1%)	
	>10 days	4 (30.8%)	33 (55.9%)	
Diabetes Mellitus	Present	6 (46.2%)	27 (45.8%)	0.980
	Absent	7 (53.8%)	32 (54.2%)	
Systemic Hypertension	Present	8 (61.5%)	24 (40.7%)	0.171
	Absent	5 (38.5%)	35 (59.3%)	
Coronary Artery Disease	Present	1 (7.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0.234
	Absent	12 (92.3%)	58 (98.3%)	
Hypothyroidism	Present	3 (23.1%)	4 (6.8%)	0.043[^]
	Absent	10 (76.9%)	55 (93.2%)	

**p value by chi-square test*

		Outcome, n(%)		p value*
		Death	Recovered	
Culture findings	Bacterial Growth	1 (7.7%)	10 (16.9%)	0.481
	Fungal Growth	0	3 (5.1%)	
	Noraml Growth/ Normal Flora	7 (53.8%)	20 (33.9%)	
	Not done	5 (38.5%)	26 (44.1%)	

**p value by chi-square test*

DISCUSSION:

In this Single centre, Retrospective medical record based cohort study we observed no significant differences in the incidence of secondary bacterial infection in COVID 19 pneumonia. The mean age of the COVID19 patients were 56 ±14.1 years. Majority were in the age group of 41- 60 years. More than half of the patients (53%) were females. Among the COVID19 patients, about 46% and 44% were diabetics and hypertensives respectively. About 3% had coronary artery disease and 10% had hypothyroidism. More than half of the COVID19 patients had more than 10 days of stay. About 36% and 42% patients had moderate and severe COVID19. Patients with severe and moderate COVID19 had significantly higher duration ($p<0.05$) of stay on comparison with mild COVID19 patients. Based on culture findings, about 15% of the COVID19 patients had secondary bacterial infection. The commonest bacteria were Pseudomonas followed by E. coli, Klebsiella and Enterococci. Among the different factors associated with culture growth, the presence of diabetes mellitus was the only significant factor associated. Diabetics was significantly associated with higher incidence of fungal infection. Among the different factors associated with death, higher age group, lower duration of hospital stay, and presence of hypothyroidism were significantly associated with bad outcome (death). Among those 11 patients with secondary bacterial

infection, 10 (91%) had recovered. There was no significant difference between culture findings and poor outcome.

CONCLUSION:

This retrospective medical record based study was conducted to asses the incidence of secondary bacterial infection in COVID 19 pneumonia and to warrant extra caution to prevent the occurrence of secondary bacterial infection and to practice appropriate antimicrobial stewardship .No significant difference between culture findings and poor outcome was found in this study Based on culture findings, about 15% of the COVID19 patients had secondary bacterial infection.. However diabetes was significantly associated with the higher incidence of fungal infection and based on the culture findings the commonest bacteria involved were Pseudomonas followed by E. coli, Klebsiella and Enterococci. Therefore diabetic management plays a key role in prevention of secondary infection

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